

Research article

Acmaeoderella (Euacmaeoderella) villosula (Steven, 1830), a new record of jewel beetles (Coleoptera: Buprestidae) from Bulgaria

Mark G. Volkovitsh¹, Vladimir Sakalian², Chavdar Gussev³, Georgi Georgiev⁴

(1) Zoological Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences, Saint Petersburg, 199034 Russia, polycest@zin.ru

(2) Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 1 Tsar Osvoboditel Blvd, 1000 Sofia, Bulgaria, vladimir.sakalian@gmail.com

(3) Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 23 Acad. G. Bonchev Street, 1113 Sofia, Bulgaria, chgussev@gmail.com

(4) Forest Research Institute, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences, 132 St Kliment Ohridski Blvd, 1756 Sofia, Bulgaria, ggeorgiev.fri@gmail.com

Abstract: *Acmaeoderella (Euacmaeoderella) villosula* (Steven, 1830) is established as a new species for Bulgaria. It is an East Mediterranean-Iranian-Turanian element of the fauna of Balkan Peninsula. This is third country report of the taxon for the Balkan region. In Bulgaria, *A. (E.) villosula* is most similar to *Acmaeoderella (E.) subcyanea* (Reitter, 1890), and this paper presents the main diagnostic characters that allow the distinction of these species. With this record, the total number of known Bulgarian *Acmaeoderella* species and subspecies increases up to 11.

Keywords: *Acmaeoderella*, Balkan Peninsula, Bulgaria, Buprestidae, Coleoptera, Polycestinae

Introduction

According to Sakalian (2003) and Volkovitsh et al. (2015) five subgenera and 10 species and subspecies of the genus *Acmaeoderella* are recorded in Bulgaria. With the new report of *A. (Euacmaeoderella) villosula* (Steven, 1830), the total number of known *Acmaeoderella* taxa in this country increases up to 11. This genus is represented in Bulgaria by the following subgenera: *Acmaeoderella* s.str. (three species and subspecies); *Liogastris* (single species); *Omphalothorax* (single species); *Carininota* (two species and subspecies) and *Euacmaeoderella* (four species including new one).

Volkovitsh et al. (2015) published key of the subfamily Polycestinae in Bulgaria. In this paper we extend this key to include new record.

Study area

Sakar is a low mountain (50 to 856 m a.s.l.) in southeastern Bulgaria, and the most northwestern part

of European Türkiye (Figs 1 and 2). The mountain stretches from northwest to southeast for 75 km, and its width in the middle reaches 35 km. The mountain is relatively deforested and with a rather dry and very warm climate. Phytogeographically it falls into the Macedonian-Thracian province of the European broad-leaved forest region. Its lowest parts are occupied by agricultural areas instead of forests. In the past, the vegetation cover was of xerothermic forest phytocoenoses, with a predominance of *Quercus pubescens* Wild. and with the participation of *Carpinus orientalis* Mill., in the eastern parts of pure forests of *Quercus frainetto* Ten. or mixed forests of *Q. frainetto* and *Q. cerris* L., and in the highest parts (Vishovgrad Peak – 856 m) – xeromesophytic forests of *Quercus petraea* subsp. *polycarpa* (Schur) Soó with the participation of *C. orientalis*, *Tilia tomentosa* Moench, etc. Part of these oak forests are still preserved, but fragmentarily, and in places secondary vegetation has been formed from forests of *C. orientalis* and especially thickets of *Palliurus spina-christii* Mill. and xerothermic grass vegetation dominated by *Chrysopogon gryllus* (L.)

Fig. 1. View of Sakar Mountain (Photo: I. Todorov).

Fig. 2. The locality of *Acmaeoderella* (*Euacmaeoderella*) *villosula* near Sladun Village (Photo: T. Ljubomirov).

Trin., *Dichanthium ischaemum* (L.) Keng, *Poa bulbosa* L. and ephemeral grass communities, made up of annual therophytes, mainly Mediterranean species of the families Poaceae and Fabaceae. The presence of chasmophyte vegetation developed mainly on silicate and less often on carbonate rocks is also characteristic. Original features of the flora and vegetation are formed by the participation in the communities of the Macedonian-Thracian floral elements – Balkan and Bulgarian endemics. The participation of steppe, Euxine and Mediterranean floral elements is also characteristic.

Near the collecting location of *Acmaeoderella (Euacmaeoderella) villosula* the herbaceous vegetation is represented by xerothermic herbaceous communities of typical pseudosteppes and petrophytic calcareous steppes. The pseudosteppe communities are of Mediterranean origin, and are dominated by annual cereals, legumes, but also include creeping low semi-shrubs, tufted wheatgrasses, etc. Typical species for these phytocoenoses are *P. bulbosa*, *Bupleurum apiculatum* Friv., *Gaudinia fragilis* (L.) P. Beauv., *Inula ensifolia* L., *Helianthemum salicifolium* L., *Trifolium scabrum* L., *Aegilops geniculata* Roth, *Psilurus aristatus* (L.) Duval-Jouve, *Ziziphora capitata* L., *Neatostema apulum* (L.) I. M. Johnst., *Trachynia distachya* (L.) Link, *Velezia rigida* L., *Scleropoa rigida* (L.) Griseb., etc. Perennial species also participate, but with low abundance, such as *C. gryllus*, *D. ischaemum*, *Achillea coarctata* Poir., *Koeleria splendens* C. Presl, *Euphorbia myrsinites* L., etc.

Materials and methods

The specimen of *Acmaeoderella (Euacmaeoderella) villosula* was collected from flower by entomological net. It is kept in the collection of Vladimir Sakalian (Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research).

Abbreviations used in the text: IBER – Institute of Biodiversity and Ecosystem Research, Bulgarian Academy of Sciences (Sofia, Bulgaria); ZIN – Zoological Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences (Saint Petersburg, Russia).

Results and discussion

The collecting locality of *Acmaeoderella (Euacmaeoderella) villosula* (Steven, 1830) is as follows:

Bulgaria, Sakar Mts, W Sladun Village, 41.8492°N, 26.4443°E, 233 m, 17.07.2024, one female specimen, T. Ljubomirov leg. A photograph of the habitat is presented on Fig. 2.

At the region around Sladun Village *Acmaeoderella (Acmaeoderella) brevipes brevipes* Kiesenwetter, 1858, *Acmaeoderella (Carininota) flavofasciata flavofasciata* (Piller & Mitterpacher, 1783), and *A. (C.) mimonti mimonti* (Boieldieu, 1865) from the tribe Acmaeoderini together with other Buprestidae taxa were collected as well.

According to Volkovitsh (2021) the known larval host plants of the species are: *Ferula rigidula* Fisch., *Malabaila dasyantha* Fisch. & C.A.Mey., *Zosima absintifolia* Link. (Apiales: Apiaceae). Because these plant species are not distributed in Bulgaria, we assume that the larva of *A. (E.) villosula* develops, most probably, in another representative of Apiaceae or in the other plant families as Asteraceae, in particular, the species of genus *Inula*.

According to Volkovitsh (2016) the general distribution of *A. (E.) villosula* so far is known as follows: Europe: Greece, North Macedonia; North Africa: Egypt, Asia: Afghanistan, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia, Cyprus, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Jordan, Lebanon, Syria, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Türkiye. As noted above in Balkan Peninsula *A. (E.) villosula* is known from Greece and North Macedonia till now. According to Mühle et al. (2000) this species is distributed in Greece in different areas at the following regions: Aegean slands, Crete, Central Greece, Ionian Islands, North Greece and Peloponnese. North Macedonia was mentioned by Volkovitsh (2016) based on the single studied specimen: Macedonia, Skopje reg., Katlanovo Village, 24.05.1996, S. Hristovski, leg. (current depositary is unknown).

According to the proposed chorology by Sakalian & Langourov (2007) the species has East Mediterranean-Iranian-Turanian range of distribution.

The information about the synonyms of *A. (E.) villosula* can be found in Volkovitsh (2016).

In Bulgaria *A. (E.) villosula* is the most similar to *A. (E.) subcyanea* (Reitter, 1890). In this paper we present the main diagnostic characters which allow to distinguish these species and extend the key of Bulgarian Polycestinae proposed by Volkovitsh et al. (2015). They are as follow:

Figs 3–8. Habitus (3, 4) and male and female antennae (5–8) of *Acmaeoderella* (*Euacmaeoderella*) *villosula* and *A. (E.) subcyanea*: 3 – *A. (E.) villosula* (female, 8.2 mm, Bulgaria, IBER); 4 – *A. (E.) subcyanea* (male, 6.3 mm, Türkiye, ZIN); 5, 6 – *A. (E.) villosula* (5 – male, 1.8 mm, Cyprus, ZIN; 6 – female, 1.9 mm, Bulgaria, IBER); 7, 8 – *A. (E.) subcyanea* (7 – male, 2.0 mm, Iran, ZIN; 8 – female, 1.8 mm, Azerbaijan, ZIN) (Photo: M.G. Volkovitsh).

18 Uniformly bronze; dorsally covered with very dense, long setose scales, on elytra twice longer than interval width, ventrally covered with the same scales much denser on the sides; antennae short nearly equal in both sexes, expanding from antennomere 5. 5.2–12.0 mm. (Volkovitsh et al., 2015, Fig. 46)
 *A. (Euacmaeoderella) vetusta* (Ménétriés)
 — Black with elytra blue rarely black or bronze, shagreened, dorsally covered with sparse short scales, on elytra not longer than interval width, ventrally covered with short scales much denser and longer on the sides of meso- and metaventrites, and abdomen; antennae sharply dimorphic, much longer and stronger expanded in males 19

19 Elytra shagreened, mostly matt, antennae expanded from antennomere 4, in male antennomeres 5–10 irregularly expanded (Fig. 7), in female transversely triangular (Fig. 8). Aedeagus as on Figs 12–14, ovipositor as on Figs 17, 18. 5.2–8.9 mm (Fig. 4)
 *A. (E.) subcyanea* (Reitter)
 — Elytra not shagreened, shiny, antennae expanded from antennomere 5, in male rarely from 4; in male antennomeres 5–10 strongly transversely triangular (Fig. 5), in female antennomeres 5–10 much weaker transversely triangular (Fig. 6). Aedeagus as on Figs 9–11, ovipositor as on Figs. 15, 16. 6.0–11.0 mm (Fig. 3)
 *A. (E.) villosula* (Steven)

Figs 9–18. Male and female genitalia of *Acmaeoderella (Euacmaeoderella) villosula* and *A. (E.) subcyanea*. 9–14 – aedeagus (9, 12 – tegumen, 10, 11, 13, 14 – penis): 9–11 – *A. (E.) villosula*; 12–14 – *A. (E.) subcyanea*. 15–18 – ovipositor: 15, 16 – *A. (E.) villosula*; 17, 18 – *A. (E.) subcyanea* (Photo: M.G. Volkovitsh).

The length of the tegumen for this group varies between 1.9–2.3 mm, the penis – 1.4–1.7 mm, the ovipositor – 2.8–3.3 mm. In *A. villosula*, the genitalia are slightly longer than in *A. subcyanea*.

The new data about distribution of *A. (E.) villosula* in Bulgaria mirrors the specific geographical position, diversity and richness of Balkan fauna where it is possible to find the representatives of many faunal

elements as Boreal, European, Mediterranean, Middle Asian, etc. (and in this case – East Mediterranean-Iranian-Turanian) together with endemics. Bulgaria is the third country, after Greece and North Macedonia, where this species has been registered on the Balkan Peninsula. It is very likely that in the future it will be collected in some other countries in this region or in Southern Europe.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank T. Ljubomirov (Sofia, Bulgaria) for collecting the specimen of *Acmaeoderella* (*Euacmaeoderella*) *villosula* (Steven, 1830). We are also thankful to him and I. Todorov (Sofia, Bulgaria) for sent us suitable photos from Sakar Mts. The study by M. G. Volkovitsh was performed within the frame of the State Projects no. 125012901042-9 of the Zoological institute, Russian Academy of Sciences.

References

- Mühle H., Brandl P., Niehuis M. 2000 Catalogus Faunae Graeciae. Coleoptera: Buprestidae. Selbstverlag, Augsburg, 254 pp.
- Sakalian V. 2003 A Catalogue of the Jewel Beetles of Bulgaria (Coleoptera: Buprestidae). Zoocartographia Balcanica. 2. Pensoft Publishers, Sofia – Moscow, 246 pp.
- Sakalian V., Langourov M. 2007 Fauna and Zoogeography of Jewel Beetles (Coleoptera: Buprestidae) in Bulgaria. In: Fet V., Popov A. (eds) Biogeography and Ecology of Bulgaria. Monographiae Biologicae, vol. 82, Springer, pp. 357–378.
- Volkovitsh M.G. 2016 Polycestinae. In: Löbl I., Löbl D. (eds) Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera. Volume 3. Scarabaeoidea – Scirtoidea – Dascilloidea – Buprestoidea – Byrrhoidea. Revised and updated edition. Brill, Leyden & Boston, pp. 438–452.
- Volkovitsh M.G. 2021 Synopsis of the Host Plants of the Palaearctic Jewel Beetles of the Tribe Acmaeoderini (Coleoptera, Buprestidae: Polycestinae). Entomological Review 101 (4): 465–518.
- Volkovitsh M.G., Sakalian V., Georgiev G. 2015 A checklist and a key to the taxa of the subfamily Polycestinae Lacordaire, 1857 (Coleoptera: Buprestidae) in Bulgaria. Acta zoologica bulgarica 67 (4): 471–478.